

Studies on Heterocyclic Compounds. Part-VI : Synthesis of Bridgehead Nitrogen Triazine and Pyrimidine Heterocycles

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New bridgehead nitrogen containing heterocycles such as thiazolotriazine (IVa and IVb), imidazolotriazine (IVc), triazinotriazine (IVd and IVe) and oxadiazolotriazine (IVf) and several of their derivatives (V) have been prepared by reacting their respective hydrazine (II) with ethylpyruvate and phenyl glyoxalic acid. The diazotization of hydrazine (II) furnished the reactive intermediates (VI) (azido form) and (VII) (tetrazole form) depending on the structure of hydrazines. These intermediates have been used to synthesise bridgehead nitrogen pyrimidine derivatives (VIII) by reacting them with diethyl fumarate. The spectral and chemical evidences show that diazotised products obtained from 2-hydrazino-4-phenyl thiazole (IIa) and 2-hydrazino benzothiazole (IIb) exist in tetrazole form (VIIa) and (VIIb), respectively, whereas the remaining four (IIa-IVf) remain in the azido form (VIc-VIf) in the solid state.

IN continuation of our studies on the chemistry of nitrogen and sulphur heterocyclic compounds¹⁻³ and in view of possible pharmacological activity of new purine analogues⁴⁻⁶ the syntheses of 6-methyl-4-phenyl-5(H) thiazolo [3,2-b]-as-triazine-5-one (IVa, R=CH₃), 3-methyl-4(H)-as-triazino [3,2-f] benzothiazol-4-one (IVb, R=CH₃), benzimidazolotriazine (IVc, R=CH₃), triazinotriazine (IVd and IVe), thiazolotriazepine (Va and Vb), benzimidazolotriazepin (Vc), thiazolotetrazole (VIIa and VIIb), thiazolopyrimidine (VIIIa and VIIIb), imidazopyrimidine (VIIIc), triazinopyrimidine (VIIId and VIIIe) and several triazepino derivatives (V) have been made in our present study. 2-Mercapto-4-phenylthiazole (Ia) was allowed to react with hydrazine hydrate to afford 4-phenylthiazolyl-2-hydrazine (IIa). Treatment of IIa with ethylpyruvate followed by hydrolysis in alkali gave the acid hydrazone (IIIa; R=methyl, R'=H). The desired 6-methyl-3-phenyl-5H-thiazolo [2,3-c]-as-triazin-5-one (IVa; R=methyl) was obtained by refluxing the acid hydrazone (IIIa; R=CH₃, R'=H) with acetic acid in good yield via a dehydrative cyclisation reaction. Similar reaction of the hydrazine (IIa) with phenyl glyoxalic acid furnished the 3,6-diphenyl-5H-thiazolo [2,3-c]-as-triazin-5-one (IVa; R=phenyl). Following the general procedures the compounds (IVb-IVf) have been prepared starting from various mercapto heterocycles (Ib-Ij). The route for the synthesis of these compounds have been presented in Scheme 1. The structure of 6-methyl-3-phenyl-5H-thiazolo [2,3-c]-as-triazine (IVa; R=CH₃) was confirmed from uv and mass spectral studies. Its uv spectra showed an intense band at 360 nm and another less prominent band in the lower wavelength of 255 nm. This is in good agreement with the observation of others^{7,8} with the 5-one triazine compounds. The mass spectral fragmentation pattern of the same

a = 4-Phenylthiazolyl-2; b = Benzothiazolyl-2; c = Benzimidazolyl-2; d = 4,5-Diphenyl-1,3,4-triazinyl-2; e = 5-Phenyl-1,3,4-triazinyl-2; f = 5-Phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolyl-2.

1. H₂N-NH₂, H₂O; 2. CH₃COOEt, NaOH and HCl;
3. CH₃COOH; 4. CH₃COCH₂COOEt, NaOH, HCl and CH₃COOH; 5. HCl, NaNO₂; 6. Diethylfumarate.

Scheme 1

compound (IVa; R=CH₃) has been presented in Scheme 2 supporting the structure. It can be seen that by the loss of carbon monoxide molecule triazolo [3,4-b] thiazole ion of m/e 215 (85%) is formed.

The reaction of hydrazino derivatives (II) with acetoacetic ester resulted in the formation of triazepino derivative (V). The nmr of thiazolotriazepine (Va) prepared by reacting the 2-hydrazino-4-phenylthiazole with acetoacetic ester showed two sharp singlet at δ 1.3 and 4.1 corresponding to methyl and methine protons, respectively besides the phenyl and

Scheme 2. Mass fragmentation pattern of IVa.

thiazole ring protons in the aromatic region confirming its structure.

Since the azido-tetrazole tautomerisation in fused tetrazole derivatives is an interesting phenomena which depends on the structure and physical state⁹⁻¹¹ of the molecule, these heterocyclic hydrazines were diazotised to get the azido (VI) derivatives which can undergo tautomerisation to give tetrazole derivatives (VII). In our present study the hydrazines (II) were diazotised with sodium nitrite and hydrochloric acid and the resulting solids were stirred in water to complete the cyclisation with a view to obtaining the tetrazole derivatives (VII). The spectral and chemical evidence showed that the diazotised products obtained from 2-hydrazino-4-phenylthiazole and 2-hydrazino-benzothiazole have predominant tetrazole structure (VIIa and VIIb) respectively whereas the others remain in the azido form (VI) in solid state. The ir spectra of the diazotised product obtained from 2-hydrazino-4-phenylthiazole in KBr disc showed no peak in the region of 2130-2160 cm^{-1} indicating the absence of

$-\bar{N}-\bar{N}\equiv N$ (azido) group. The ir spectra pattern also did not change in the chloroform solution indicating predominant tetrazole structure, although its 3-methyl derivative showed the phenomena of tautomerism¹². The appearance of intense band at 2145 cm^{-1} in case of the diazo derivatives of 2-hydrazino-benzimidazole in KBr disc indicates that it exists exclusively in the azido form (VIc) in solid state at room temperature. The chemical evidence in support of the structure VIIa, in case of the diazotised product of IIa was known from their reaction with diethyl fumarate. When the former is reacted with diethyl fumarate at 120° for 1 hr, a yellow crystalline compound, m.p. 227° was obtained in 80% yield corresponding to the structure VIIIa, whereas the latter (VIc) reacted with diethyl fumarate at room temperature furnishing VIIIc in quantitative yield. The formation of VIIIa under the reaction condition applied could be a supporting evidence for the formation of azido form (VIa) at the expense of tetrazole form (VIIa) with the rise of temperature whereas the formation of VIIIc at room temperature indicates the predominance of azido form VIc. The same phenomena was observed in case of the diazo derivative of IIb. The likely mechanism for this type of reactions may be either the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition or the addition of nitrine intermediate to

this dienophile (Scheme 3). Reynold *et al*¹³ and Faure *et al*¹⁴ have also established the predominance of azido structure in case of VIc and tetrazole structure in case of VIIb, respectively from nmr and dipole measurement studies.

Scheme 3. Formation of pyrimidinone (VIII) from reaction of azide (VI) with diethyl fumarate.

The bactericidal and fungicidal potencies of the compounds are under study.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Model-291 spectrophotometer.

2-Mercapto-4-phenylthiazole (IIa)¹⁵, 2-mercaptobenzimidazole (IIc)¹⁶, 2-mercapto-5,6-diphenyl-1,3,4-triazine (IIb)¹⁷, 2-mercapto-5-phenyl-1,3,4-triazine (IIe)¹⁸ and 2-mercapto-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (IIf)¹⁹ of m.p. 155, 299, >250, 115-116 and 162-164°, respectively were prepared by literature procedure.

(4-Phenylthiazolyl-2)hydrazine (IIa) : 2-Mercapto-4-phenylthiazole (1.9 g; 0.01 mole) and hydrazine hydrate (80%; 20 ml) were taken in a conical flask and the mixture was heated under reflux for 2 hr. After cooling, colourless needles separated, m.p. 172°, yield 1.3 g (70%). (Found : S, 16.68. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{S}$ requires S, 16.75%).

(Benzothiazolyl-2)hydrazine (IIb) : This was prepared by taking 2-mercaptobenzothiazole (6.68 g; 0.04 mole) and hydrazine hydrate (80%; 20 ml) and following the above procedure as fine needles, m.p. 192° (lit. m.p. 192-94°), yield 62%. (Found : S, 19.04. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{S}$ requires S, 19.39%).

Ethyl- α -oxopropionate(benzothiazol-2-yl)hydrazone (IIIf; $R=\text{CH}_3$, $R'=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) : A solution of the hydrazino benzothiazole (1.65 g; 0.01 mole) and ethylpyruvate (1.16 g; 0.01 mole) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 6 hr. The solvent was evaporated

and the residue dissolved in ethanol. After cooling, the oxopropionyl derivative separated as colourless solid, m.p. 115°, yield 52%. (Found : S, 12.05. $C_{11}H_{13}N_3SO_2$ requires S, 12.16%).

Ethyl- α -oxopropionate(4-phenylthiazol-2-yl) hydrazone (IIIa; $R=CH_3$, $R'=C_2H_5$) of m.p. 154° was obtained in 60% yield by following the above procedure by reacting the hydrazino derivative (IIa) with ethylpyruvate. (Found : S, 11.54. $C_{11}H_{13}N_3SO_2$ requires S, 11.68%).

α -Oxopropionic acid(benzothiazol-2-yl) hydrazone (IIIb; $R'=H$, $R=CH_3$) : A solution of the hydrazono ester (0.263 g; 0.001 mole) and sodium hydroxide (80 mg; 0.002 mole) in ethanol-water (1 : 1) (20 ml) was refluxed for 4 hr. The solution was acidified with dil. hydrochloric acid. The precipitate was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to give 70% of the desired product, m.p. 217°. (Found : S, 13.45. $C_{10}H_9O_2N_3S$ requires S, 13.61%).

α -Oxopropionic acid(4-phenylthiazolyl-2) hydrazone (IIIb; $R'=H$, $R=CH_3$) of m.p. 163° was obtained by following the general work up procedure, yield 60%. (Found : S, 13.05. $C_{11}H_{10}N_3SO$ requires S, 13.11%).

6-Methyl-5(H)-as-triazino [3,2-f] benzothiazol-5-one (IVb; $R=CH_3$) : A solution of oxopropionic acid (0.2 g) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 days. The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue recrystallised from ethylacetate-chloroform, m.p. 197°. (Found : S, 14.46. $C_8H_9N_3OS$ requires S, 14.67%); λ_{max}^{EtOH} (nm) :

352, 260 ($\epsilon=365$); ν_{max}^{KBr} (cm^{-1}) : 2870 ($-CH_2-$ stretch), 1730 (C=O), 1610 (C-N stretch).

6-Methyl-3-phenyl-5(H)-thiazolo [2,3-e]-as-triazone-5(1H) (IVa; $R=CH_3$) of m.p. 206° was also obtained in 40% yield by following the above procedure starting with IIIa ($R=CH_3$, $R'=H$); λ_{max}^{EtOH} (nm) : 360 ($\epsilon=1.2 \times 10^4$), 255 ($\epsilon=355$).

Tetrazolo [5,1-b] benzothiazole (VIIb) : A solution of hydrazinobenzothiazole (IIb) (1.65 g; 0.01 mole) in 6 N HCl (10 ml) was kept in an ice bath at 0°. A portion of the hydrochloride of the hydrazino derivative separated. To this suspension sodium nitrite in 10 ml of water was added dropwise while maintaining the temperature at 0°. After the addition was complete the stirring was continued for an additional 0.5 hr at room temperature and the precipitate collected. It was suspended in water and stirred at room temperature overnight. Collection of the precipitate followed by recrystallisation from water produced the desired compound, m.p. 108°, yield 85%. (Found : S, 18.02. $C_7H_4N_4S$ requires S, 18.18%); ν_{max}^{KBr} (cm^{-1}) : 1605 (C-N stretch).

3-Phenyl-tetrazolo [5,1-b] thiazole (VIIa) : It was prepared by the diazotisation of 2-hydrazino-4-phenyl thiazole (1.91 g; 0.01 mole) in 6 N HCl

(10 ml) and sodium nitrite in 10 ml of water by the above procedure, m.p. 134°, yield 50%. (Found : S, 15.68. $C_9H_8N_4S$ requires S, 15.83%).

2-Azidobenzimidazole (VIc) : The hydrazinobenzimidazole (1.48 g; 0.01 mole) in 6 N HCl (20 ml) was diazotised at 0° using sodium nitrite solution in water. After diazotisation it was stirred for an additional half an hour at room temperature and the precipitate was collected, m.p. 182°, yield 60%; ν_{max}^{KBr} (cm^{-1}) : 2130 (typical N_3 band), 1600 (C=N stretch).

Reaction of the diazotised product of IIa with diethyl fumarate to obtain 3-phenyl-7-carboethoxy-5(H)-thiazolo [2,3-a] pyrimidine-5-one (VIIIa) : A mixture of the diazotised product (0.202 g) and diethylfumarate (0.172 g) was heated on an oil bath at 120° for 1 hr. After cooling to room temperature the reaction mixture was treated with cyclohexane and kept overnight. The solid obtained was recrystallised from rectified spirit as yellow needles, m.p. 227°, yield 0.187 g (70%). (Found : S, 11.87. $C_{15}H_{13}N_2O_3S$ requires S, 11.94%); ν_{max}^{KBr} (cm^{-1}) : 1760 (C=O), 1710 (ester carbonyl), 1640 (C=N); nmr ($CDCl_3$) δ : 1.3 (t, 3H, CH_3), 4.45 (q, 2H, $-CH_2-$), 7.3 (s, 1H pyrimidine H6), 7.7 (m, 5H, phenylproton); MS : m/e 300 (M^+).

Reaction of diazotised product of IIb with diethyl fumarate to obtain VIIIb : The mixture of the diazotised product (0.176 g) and diethyl fumarate (0.172 g) was heated on an oil bath at 120° for 3 hr, the product isolated after trituration with ether and recrystallised from rectified spirit as deep yellow needles, m.p. 213°, yield 0.156 g (65%). (Found : S, 11.80. $C_{11}H_{10}N_2O_3S$ requires S, 11.85%); ν_{max}^{KBr} (cm^{-1}) : 1760 (C=O), 1700 (ester carbonyl); MS : m/e 274 (M^+).

Reaction of diazotised product of IIc with diethyl fumarate to obtain VIIIc : A solution of the diazotised product (0.159 g) in ethanol (20 ml) was treated with a solution of diethyl fumarate (0.172 g) in ethanol (5 ml). An exothermic reaction took place immediately and a deep yellow crystalline solid separated, m.p. 175°, yield 0.15 g (50%).

Similarly, compound VIII d, m.p. > 250°, (Found : N, 20.13. $C_{21}H_{16}N_4O_3$ requires N, 20.27%); VIII e, m.p. 195°, (Found : N, 26.58. $C_{11}H_{13}N_4O_3$ requires N, 26.83%); VIII f, m.p. 186°, (Found : N, 24.45. $C_{14}H_{11}N_3O_3$ requires N, 24.57%) were obtained by room temperature reaction.

Ethyl β -oxobutyrate(benzothiazol-2-yl) hydrazone : 2-Hydrazinobenzothiazole (0.330 g; 0.002 mole) and acetoacetic ester (0.260 g; 0.002 mole) in absolute alcohol (5 ml) was refluxed for 6 hr. The solvent was evaporated and the residue crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 215°, yield 45%. (Found : S, 11.03. $C_{11}H_{11}N_3O_2S$ requires S, 11.55%).

β -Oxobutanoic acid(benzothiazolyl-2) hydrazone : A solution of hydrazino ester (0.277 g; 0.001 mole)

TABLE 1

Compound	Hydrazines (II)			Azido derivatives (VI)			Important ir bands in cm^{-1} for azido group
	m.p. °C	Mol. formula	% Nitrogen Found/(Calcd.)	m.p. °C	Mol. formula	% Nitrogen Found/(Calcd.)	
c	157	$\text{C}_7\text{H}_9\text{N}_4$	40.45 (40.58)	182	$\text{C}_7\text{H}_9\text{N}_5$	39.76 (44.02)	2130
d	162-164	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_5$	26.50 (26.62)	154	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_6$	33.34 (33.57)	2150
e	220	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_5$	38.21 (38.81)	182	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_6$	45.60 (45.72)	—
f	>250	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_4\text{O}$	31.56 (31.82)	145	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_5\text{O}$	37.21 (37.48)	2145

TABLE 2

Compound	Hydrazones (III)				Triazines (IV)			
	R	R'	m.p. °C	Mol. formula	% Nitrogen Found/(Calcd.)	m.p. °C	Mol. formula	% Nitrogen Found/(Calcd.)
a	Phenyl	H	143	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}$	12.85 (13.00)	185	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{OS}$	15.23 (15.34)
b	Phenyl	H	172	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}$	14.86 (14.96)	200	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{OS}$	14.98 (15.05)
c	Methyl	ethyl	230	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$	24.42 (24.45)	—	—	—
c	Methyl	H	291	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$	27.78 (27.86)	213	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{O}$	27.95 (28.00)
d*	Methyl	H	>250	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_5\text{O}_2$	19.07 (19.17)	224	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_5\text{O}$	22.04 (22.22)
e	Methyl	ethyl	210	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_5\text{O}_2$	22.32 (22.40)	—	—	—
e	Methyl	H	225	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_5\text{O}_2$	24.74 (24.84)	246	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_9\text{N}_5\text{O}$	29.57 (29.78)
f*	Methyl	H	>250	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$	22.68 (22.71)	234	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$	26.39 (26.42)

* The corresponding esters were obtained as oily mass which were used directly without further purification.

and sodium hydroxide (0.08 g; 0.002 mole) in ethanol-water (1:1) (10 ml) was refluxed for 4 hr. After cooling, it was acidified with dil. hydrochloric acid. The precipitate was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to give 60% of the product, m.p. 222°. (Found: S, 12.84. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_5\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires S, 12.54%).

5-Methyl-7(H)-1,3,4-triazepino [2,3-a] benzothiazol-7-one (Vb): The acid was cyclised in glacial acetic acid after refluxing for 3 days. The solvent was evaporated and the residue recrystallised from ethyl acetate-chloroform (1:1) mixture, m.p. 157°. (Found: S, 17.39. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{N}_5\text{SO}$ requires S, 17.44%).

The other triazepino derivatives Vb (m.p. 157°) and Vc (m.p. >250°) were also prepared in 55% and 60% yields.

The physical and analytical data of other hydrazines (II) and azido derivatives (V) and hydrazones (III) and triazine derivatives (IV) have been presented in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

References

1. K. SAHU, R. K. BEHERA, R. C. PATTNAIK, A. NAYAK and G. B. BEHERA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, **18B**, 557.
2. A. K. MUND, R. K. BEHERA, A. NAYAK and G. B. BEHERA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, **17B**, 404.
3. S. NAIK, R. K. BEHERA and A. NAYAK, *Indian J. Chem.*, (in press).
4. I. LALEZARI and A. SHAFICE, *J. Het. Chem.*, 1971, **8**, 835.
5. H. GOLGOLALE, I. LALEZARI and G. GOHARI-LHOSSENI, *J. Het. Chem.*, 1973, **10**, 387.
6. A. A. SANTILLI, A. C. SEATESE and D. H. KIM, *J. Het. Chem.*, 1976, **13**, 135.
7. C. F. ALLEN, H. R'BRCLFUSS, D. M. BURNES, G. A. REYNOLDS, J. F. TINKER and J. A. VAN ALLAN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, **24**, 779.
8. D. W. DUNWELL and D. EVANS, *J. Chem. Soc. C*, 1971, 2094.
9. M. TISLER, *Synthesis*, 1973, 123.
10. J. ELGUERO, C. MARZIN, A. R. KATRIZKY and P. LINDA in "Tautomerism of Heterocycles, Advances in Heterocyclic Chemistry", Academic Press, New York, N. Y., 1976, Suppl. Vol. I.
11. G. WENTRUP, *Tetrahedron*, 1976, **26**, 4969; J. N. SHEINER *et al.*, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk SSSR*, 1961, **141**, 1389.
12. J. ELGUERO, R. FAURE, J. P. GALY and E. J. VINCENT, *Bull. Soc. Chem. Belg.*, 1975, **84**, 1205.
13. G. A. REYNOLDS, J. A. VAN ALLAN and J. F. TINKER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, **24**, 1205.
14. R. FAURE, J. P. GALY, E. J. VINCENT, J. P. FAYET, P. MAURET, M. C. VERTUT and J. ELGUERO, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1977, **55**, 1728.
15. A. K. MISHRA, M.Sc. Thesis, Utkal University, 1969.
16. A. LELLMANN, *Ann.*, 1883, **9**, 221.
17. K. C. JOSHI and V. N. PATHAK, *J. Het. Chem.*, 1980, **17**, 789.
18. V. RANGA RAO and V. R. SRINIVASAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 509.
19. N. A. DAHLER and W. C. DOYLE, JR., *U. S. Patent*, 3808, 223.